

EFFECTS OF LOAD COMBINATION ON BIAXIAL BUCKLING OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE RECTANGULAR PLATES

Young S. Kim and Suong V. Hoa

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Concordia University
1455 Maisonneuve Blvd. W., Montreal, Canada H3G 1M8

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ABSTRACT

The effects of axial load ratio on the buckling behavior of laminated composite rectangular plates subjected to biaxial loads were numerically analyzed and experimentally determined. A slightly modified plate specimens was used in the experiments to determine the critical buckling load and postbuckling behavior under various combinations of axial loads. To investigate the admissibility of the modified plate specimen as a substitute of the ideal plate, buckling deflection behaviors and various strain responses of the modified plate were compared with the results of ideal plate by nonlinear finite element analysis . Also, the uniformity of the strains on the edges of the modified plate specimen was investigated by experiments and numerical analysis.

Critical buckling load was determined from energy theorem and linear finite element analysis. In experimental works, the critical buckling loads were determined from Southwell Plot and maximum deflection measurement method. These theoretical and experimental data for critical buckling loads were compared with the results of nonlinear finite element analyses for various combinations of axial loads. Nonlinear finite element analyses and experimental works concurrently revealed that : when the load combination was closer to the uniaxial buckling condition, the buckling responses of plate showed a clear bifurcation behavior and a quicker growth to the full-developed postbuckling state, but when the load combination was closer to the uniform biaxial buckling state, the buckling response of plate showed an obscure bifurcation behavior and a slower growth to the full-developed postbuckling state.

Key words:biaxial buckling, axial load combination, modified plate specimen, critical load, Southwell Plot, maximum deflection measurement method .

1 INTRODUCTION

Plate may undergo buckling in the presence of high inplane loadings. When a plate is subjected to inplane load, it remains in a stable equilibrium state until the inplane load reached the critical buckling load. If the plate is exposed to a small enough increment of load beyond the critical buckling load, the plate can not remain in the primary equilibrium state but it may shift to another secondary equilibrium state having a large lateral deflection, which is undesirable behavior as a structural element.

Figure 1: Schematic drawings of the biaxial loading devices with a rectangular specimen, a) Ideal setup, b) Modified setup.

Generally simply supported rectangular plates are likely exposed to uniaxial load or biaxial load in the structural applications and they generate a kind of biharmonic deflection curves as their buckling mode shapes. Even though a plate is exposed to uniaxial load only, during the buckling process, the plate may experience various biaxial stress and strain state due to the correlation between axial load and reaction force of the other sides. Thus, bi-axial buckling analyses and experiments may produce more relevant design parameters than conventional uniaxial analyses and experiments in the design of plate structure. To the authors' knowledge, no experimental work has been successfully done on the buckling of composite plate under simultaneous bi-directional loadings even though a significant amount of experimental work has been done on uniaxial buckling. Some theoretical treatments for the bi-axial buckling of laminated plates can be found in open literature [1,2].

However, here we have an experimental obstacle in practical arrangement of biaxial testing for the rectangular plate specimen. It is the interference among four supporting grips at each corner during the continuous biaxial compression process as shown in Figure 1:a). One way to overcome this obstacle is to leave the four corners as unbounded. This model revealed a premature fracture at each point of $A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2, \dots$, due to the cutting action of loading fixtures. Finally the specimen was modified by cutting out the corner area along the line of A_1A_2, B_1B_2, \dots , as shown in Figure 1:b). This final model does not have exactly the same shape as the ideal plate. However, if the cut sizes were kept small relative to the plate dimension, the buckling response was quite close to that of ideal specimen[3]. Modified specimens were manufactured with NCT-301(Newport Composites Ltd.) composites at Concordia University. Figure 2 and Table 1 present the dimensions and engineering data of the specimens.

2 PLATE BUCKLING THEORY

2.1 Energy Equation for Plate Buckling

Buckling formulation can be constructed from the minimum potential energy theorem. It simply means that the buckling starts at the stationary value of the total potential energy, L , which is the sum of the strain energy, U , and the potential energy, V . Considering a symmetrically laminated rectangular plate subjected to the inplane loads as described in Figure 2 and Table 1, the governing equation of plate buckling can be presented as follows.

Figure 2: Dimensions, strain-gauge positions and engineering constants of modified experimental specimens.

$$\delta(L) = \delta(U + V) \quad (1)$$

where

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^a \int_0^b \left\{ D_{11} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 + D_{22} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \right)^2 + 2D_{12} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} + 4D_{66} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 + 4 \left[D_{16} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} + D_{26} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \right] \right\} dx dy \quad (2)$$

$$V = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^a \int_0^b \left\{ N_x \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 + N_y \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2 + 2N_{xy} \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right\} dx dy \quad (3)$$

Applying equations (2) and (3) onto equation (1) yields

$$D_{11} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + D_{22} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial y^4} + 4 \left[D_{16} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^3 \partial y} + D_{26} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x \partial y^3} \right] = N_x \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + 2N_{xy} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} + N_y \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \quad (4)$$

From above governing differential equation, $D_{16} = D_{26} = 0$ for specially orthotropic laminated plate. By assuming the plate deflection function as a double Fourier series which satisfies the simply supported boundary conditions, critical buckling load can be obtained as follows.

$$w = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_{mn} \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b} \quad (5)$$

$$N_{xcr} = \frac{\pi^2 [D_{11} m^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) m^2 n^2 R^2 + D_{22} n^4 R^4]}{R^2 b^2 (m^2 + k n^2 R^2)}$$

$$P_{xcr} = b N_{xcr} \quad (6)$$

where, $m, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, $R = \frac{a}{b}$ and $k = \frac{N_y}{N_x}$.

Figure 3: a) Sketch of admissible simply supported boundary conditions, b) Axial load vs. deflection responses by nonlinear finite element analyses for Plate Type #2.

Figure 4: Biaxial buckling behaviors between ideal specimen and modified specimen setup with $N_y=N_x$, a) Numerical(NFEA) and experimental results for ideal, corner-free and corner-cut plate specimen by Plate Type #2, b) Numerical(NFEA) results for ideal and corner-cut plate specimen by Plate Type #1.

2.2 Boundary Conditions

Selecting a proper set of boundary conditions which guarantee a unique solution to the assumed governing deflection function and which satisfy the actual supporting conditions is crucially important in the plate buckling analyses. In view of experimental works on buckling of rectangular plates under simply supported conditions, the boundary conditions are actually changing from initial prebuckled state to final postbuckled state. Let us consider the case in which a fully simply supported plate is compressed uniaxially or biaxially with 4-rigid supporting grips. The necessary boundary conditions for this problem can be established as follows.

$$\{N_n \neq 0 \text{ and } N_{ns} \neq 0\} \quad \text{and} \quad \{w = M_n = 0\} \quad (7)$$

$$\{N_n = 0 \text{ and } N_{ns} = 0\} \quad \text{and} \quad \{w = M_n = 0\} \quad (8)$$

Equation(7) represents a simply supported boundary condition of load-acting sides, like the boundaries of biaxially loaded plate, as shown in Figure 3: a-i), a-ii) and a-iii). Equation(8) represents a simply supported boundary condition of load-inactive sides and it would happen in the uniaxial buckling of plate as shown in Figure 3: a-iv).

Figure 5: Southwell Plot to determine the critical buckling load from experimental results, a) by x-axis uniaxial loading, b) by y-axis uniaxial loading.

3 NUMERICAL ANALYSES AND EXPERIMENTS

ANSYS finite element program[4] was used to investigate the admissibility of the modified plate specimen as a substitute of the ideal plate and the effect of load combination of the biaxially loaded plate. 8-node multi-layered shell element was used and each model was meshed as 120 ~ 220 elements. Critical buckling load was simply computed by linear finite element method(LFEA) with full subspace eigenvalue extraction approach by controlling the maximum error norm to less than 10^{-7} .

Nonlinear finite element analyses(NFEA) were performed to have more accurate buckling deformations and various strain behavior between ideal and modified plate. A small initial deflection, less than 0.5mm, was prescribed by lateral pressure in prebuckling state. To find more clear buckling points, 25 and 10 steps of load increment were imposed on Plate Type # 1 and #2 with different density as shown in Figures 3:b), 4, 6 and 7. The convergence was checked by controlling the deflection error norm, Δu , to be less than $10^{-3}mm$, with iteration up to 25 times in each step of load increment[4].

The biaxial testing machine was designed and constructed at Concordia University. It comprises with four independent hydraulic cylinder of 100 kN capacity, loading devices controlled by four LVDTs, load cells and separated power unit. All the strain and deflection data was obtained for various load combination with two types of specimens by changing the load combination to encompass uniaxial and biaxial buckling as shown in Figures 9 and 10.

4 DISCUSSION

The validity of the modified specimen as a substitute of the ideal one can be discussed by comparing the deflection behavior and strain responses between modified plate and ideal specimen which were obtained from nonlinear finite element analysis. Figure 4 represents maximum displacement(at plate center) vs. biaxial buckling load, where the trends of plots are same and a parallel transitions are found between ideal and modified specimen. It means the modified specimen is adequate to describe the buckling deflection of ideal plate by compensating the buckling load, because deflection behaviors are same but critical buckling loads have a gap according to the cut ratio. Also, the strain responses of the plate's center or plate's edge are well corresponded between ideal and modified plate from Figure 6. More details can be found in authors' previous paper[3].

Figure 6: Strain responses at plate center and edge between ideal and modified plate specimen by NFEA with $N_y=N_x$, a) Ideal plate, b) Modified plate, Plate Type #2.

Figure 7: Strain responses of uniaxial buckling by y-axis loading, a) y-strain on the edge of #3-#4-#5. b) x-strain on the edge of #8-#6-#7.

On the other hand, the effect of load combination can be debated from the experimental and NFEA results as shown in Figure 3:b), 4, 6:b), 7, 9 and 10. Comparing the trends of maximum displacement between full biaxial and uniaxial buckling from Figures 3:b) and 9, uniaxial buckling reveals more clear bifurcating behavior than biaxial state. In Figures 6:b), 7 and 10, uniaxial loaded plate experiences a severe simple compressions at the point of bifurcation, and also, a quick growth of postbuckling displacement is found. Southwell Plot[5] was applied as an extreme buckling criterion and maximum deflection measurement method was employed as a full-developed postbuckling criterion, which is comparing the maximum deflection and the plate thickness(maximum displacement \geq plate thickness). Figure 8 shows the experimental results for critical buckling load distributions, which determined by above mentioned two criteria for various load combinations. It was compared with the theoretical criterion and LFEA results based on energy theorem. This figure strongly supports aforementioned discussions. It shows that the flexural stiffness ratio, D_{11}/D_{22} , may affect to the critical buckling loads in the case of ultimate load combination like uniaxial buckling of laminated plates.

Figure 8: Critical buckling load distributions for various axial-load combinations by Plate Type #2, a) Determined from Southwell Plot, b) Determined from maximum deflection measurement method(max.disp.> thickness).

5 CONCLUSION

A modified plate specimen has been obtained to determine the critical buckling load and postbuckling behavior of biaxial buckling of laminated rectangular plate. The effect of load combination is that: when the load combination is closer to the uniaxial buckling condition, N_x or N_y only, the buckling responses shows a clear bifurcation behavior and a quicker growth to the postbuckling state, but when the load combination is closer to the full biaxial buckling state, $N_x = N_y$, the buckling response shows an obscure bifurcation behavior and a slower growth to the full-developed postbuckling state. Also, the flexural stiffness ratio, D_{11}/D_{22} , may affect to the critical buckling loads in uniaxial buckling.

References

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Figure 9: A typical experimental response of deflections(max. displacement), a) by full biaxial loading, $N_y=N_x$, b) by x-axis uniaxial loading, $N_x=1 \& N_y=0$, c) y-axis uniaxial loading, $N_y=1 \& N_x=0$.

Figure 10: Experimental strain responses of plate buckling, a) Strain #1 & #2 with $N_y=N_x$, b) Strain #1.#4 with $N_y=1 \& N_x=0$, c) Strain #3.#4 with $N_y=1 \& N_x=0$.